

Asymptotic analysis of the eigenstructure of the two-layer model and a new family of criteria for evaluating the model hyperbolicity

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ABSTRACT

Two-layer and multi-layer depth-averaged models have become popular for simulating exchange flows, seawater currents and geophysical flows. The partial differential equation systems associated with these models are similar to the single-layer shallow-water model. Yet, their eigenstructures are more complex owing to the pressure coupling between the layers. Such models occasionally lose their hyperbolic character, which may lead to numerical issues. A physical explanation is that Kelvin-Helmholtz type instabilities arise at the layers' interface, if the velocity difference between the layers becomes sufficiently large. A way to avoid the hyperbolicity loss is to locally introduce an extra momentum exchange between the layers, assessable from the system eigenstructure and aimed at roughly mimicking the dynamical effects of such instabilities. To better understand the hyperbolicity conditions, the eigenstructure of the two-layer model is methodically studied by an asymptotic analysis. The analysis for the limiting cases, where the layers' thicknesses are either comparable or very different from each other, reveals new stability criteria. These analytical criteria are, then, exploited to design a new family of approximate criteria, valid for any flow condition. Numerical investigations demonstrate the reliability of this approach, which can be easily implemented in numerical schemes for preserving the hyperbolicity.

1. Introduction

Shallow-water equations (de Saint Venant, 1871) and depth-averaged models (e.g. Savage and Hutter, 1991; Pudasaini, 2012) are widely employed to simulate free surface flows characterized by a thin flow depth, and are particularly suitable for describing natural phenomena, such as floods and geophysical flows (e.g. Fraccarollo and Toro, 1995; Ancy et al., 2008; Sarno et al., 2011a; Sarno et al., 2013; Papa et al., 2018). The popularity of such models is favoured by the fact that, different from a three dimensional approach, they allow a straightforward and fast numerical integration, typically based on finite difference or finite volume schemes. Multi-layer depth-averaged models represent an extension of single-layer models and have recently gained attention in hydraulic engineering for their capability of describing the dynamics of stratified flows. Analogous to the shallow-water model, they can be obtained by depth-averaging the mass and momentum balance equations across the different layers and by subsequently simplifying the resulting equations by means of a suitable asymptotic approxima-

tion (e.g. Savage and Hutter, 1991). The capabilities of these models in capturing the dynamics of different superimposed flows allow a more accurate description of the flow dynamics along the transverse-to-flow direction with reasonable computational costs. A two-layer approach has been successfully adopted for describing seawater currents with small density gradients (Castro et al., 2004), gravity currents (Adduce et al., 2012; La Rocca et al., 2012) and the saltwater intrusion in stratified estuaries (Krvavica and Ružić, 2020). Moreover, two-layer models have been proposed for modelling stratified geophysical flows, such as debris flows and avalanches (Fernández-Nieto et al., 2008; Luca et al., 2009; Doyle et al., 2010; Canestrelli et al., 2012; Sarno et al., 2014; Meng et al., 2017), which often exhibit a rheological stratification, especially influenced by the presence of side walls (e.g. Armanini et al., 2005; Sarno et al., 2011b; Sarno et al., 2018a; Sarno et al., 2018b; Carleo et al., 2019). A multi-layer model was introduced by Audusse (2005) to describe free surface flows of a Newtonian fluid in a computationally more efficient way than the 3D Navier-Stokes equations. As well, a multi-layer approach, based on piecewise smooth weak solutions, has been recently

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proposed by Fernández-Nieto et al. (2014, 2016) to describe Newtonian and dense granular flows.

Focusing on the case of the two-layer model (Long, 1956; Armi, 1986), it should be recalled that its partial differential equation (PDE) system is non-strictly hyperbolic, due to the pressure coupling between the layers. Namely, two of the propagation speeds of the infinitesimal perturbations may become complex numbers, which may lead to instabilities of the numerical solution (e.g. Castro et al., 2011). The mathematical structure of the two-layer model is similar to the two-phase model (e.g. Keyfitz et al., 2003; Pelanti et al., 2008), which is well-known to lose its hyperbolic character when the phase velocities are too different from each other. Under these circumstances these models become of mixed hyperbolic-elliptic type (e.g. Keyfitz, 1987), which poses several open questions about the correct boundary conditions, the validity of the exact solution and, not least, the stability of the numerical approximation. From the viewpoint of physics the hyperbolicity loss is often associated with the onset of Kelvin-Helmholtz type instabilities at the interface (von Helmholtz, 1868), which cause the occurrence of an intermediate mixing layer of finite thickness. Since the two-layer is a simplified model of reality unable to describe the mixing layer, several numerical-phenomenological approaches have been proposed to get around the problem of the hyperbolicity loss.

The parabolization of the PDE system by introducing some small artificial viscosity in the PDE model or at the level of the numerical scheme would circumvent the hyperbolicity issue (e.g. Fjordholm, 2012; Etrati and Frigaard, 2018). Yet, this modification often causes unrealistically smeared solutions, if it is not justified on a physical basis. Moreover, different from models with a finite physically-based viscosity, introducing some artificial viscosity, which decreases with the mesh refinement, might not always yield a meaningful solution in the vanishing viscosity limit (Keyfitz et al., 2003). In several application-oriented works the issue related to the hyperbolicity loss was apparently overcome by considering the real part of the PDE system eigenvalues (e.g. Savary and Zech, 2007; Chen and Peng, 2006; Chen et al., 2007; Spinewine et al., 2011; Canestrelli et al., 2012). Yet, these approaches basically rely on the intrinsic diffusion of the numerical scheme, and may still experience oscillations of the numerical solution, if the mesh is refined (Greco et al., 2008; Castro et al., 2011). Abgrall and Karni (2009) introduced auxiliary variables to enforce a finite relaxation time for the pressure coupling between the layers, which from the physical viewpoint is similar to assuming a finite speed of the pressure waves along the transverse-to-flow direction (Chiapolino and Saurel, 2018). This method ensures that the modified PDE system is strictly hyperbolic but causes the uncoupling of the layers' propagation speeds, which is undesirable (e.g. Audusse, 2005). Castro et al. (2012) attempted to describe the evolution of the intermediate mixing layer by locally shifting from two-layer to a three-layer model. However, this approach is computationally more expensive and does not completely solve the issue of the hyperbolicity loss, since even the more sophisticated three layer model is only conditionally hyperbolic.

Another physically based approach to avoid the loss of hyperbolicity consists of introducing an extra momentum exchange between the layers, so as to keep the solution within the hyperbolic region. Namely, renouncing to describe the dynamics of the mixing layer, the dynamical effects of the interface instabilities on the two layers are approximately accounted for. To determine the proper amount of this momentum exchange, Castro et al. (2011) proposed to use an approximate hyperbolicity criterion, suitable for Boussinesq flows (i.e. stratified flows with small density differences). A generalization of this approach, valid for any density difference, is given by Sarno et al. (2017), where the system hyperbolicity is analytically checked by calculating the discriminant of the characteristic polynomial associated with the

eigenvalue problem. However, this approach requires a more computationally expensive iterative algorithm. To speed-up the method by Sarno et al. (2017), Krvavica et al. (2018) proposed to calculate the discriminant and the entire eigenvalues' set by the Ferrari's formula for quartic equations (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1965). Yet, as reported also by Krvavica et al. (2018), the Ferrari's analytical roots are prone to round-off errors, which may become relevant if the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial span over different orders of magnitude (e.g. Strobach, 2010).

Considering these difficulties and also that the available analytical formulae are algebraically too complicated to reveal the essential features of the two-layer model, in this work we systematically studied the eigenstructure of the model by asymptotic analysis. Different assumptions on the variables involved in the system stability are alternatively made. By considering the two limiting cases where the layers thicknesses are comparable and very different from each other, we found new analytical stability criteria, valid for any velocity difference and density ratio. Then, with the help of an extensive numerical investigation, general stability conditions are obtained by regularizing the two limiting cases.

The paper is organized as follows. The two-layer model and the issues related to the hyperbolicity loss are recalled in Section 2. The asymptotic analyses are reported in Section 3. In Section 4 the reliability of the new stability criteria is numerically investigated and a family of approximate stability criteria, valid for any flow condition, is proposed. In Section 5 the new stability criteria are implemented in the numerical treatment for preserving the hyperbolicity. The conclusions are summarized in Section 6.

2. The two-layer model and the hyperbolicity loss

The two-layer depth-averaged model describes the motion of two superimposed immiscible fluids and can be derived by a suitable asymptotic simplification of the depth-averaged mass and momentum balance equations, written separately for each layer. Depending on the specific physical problem, the source terms of the model vary from case to case. Here, we are interested in the essential properties of the two-layer model. Thus, we neglect all additional source terms, depending on dissipative forces or mass exchanges between the layers. Considering an orthogonal Cartesian frame of reference, O_{xy} , with x parallel to the main flow direction and y being oriented opposite to the gravity vector \mathbf{g} , and denoting the upper and lower layers with subscripts 1 and 2 respectively, the two-layer model in one space variable x is written as (e.g. Kim and Leveque, 2008)

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t h_1 + \partial_x (h_1 u_1) = 0 \\ \partial_t (h_1 u_1) + \partial_x \left(\frac{1}{2} g h_1^2 + h_1 u_1^2 \right) + g h_1 \partial_x h_2 = -g h_1 \partial_x b \\ \partial_t h_2 + \partial_x (h_2 u_2) = 0 \\ \partial_t (h_2 u_2) + \partial_x \left(\frac{1}{2} g h_2^2 + h_2 u_2^2 \right) + \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} g h_2 \partial_x h_1 = -g h_2 \partial_x b. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, h_i , u_i and ρ_i are the thickness, the depth-averaged velocity and the density of the i -th layer (with $i = 1, 2$), while t is time and $b(x)$ is the basal topography, see the sketch in Fig. 1. The unknown functions are $\mathbf{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4)^T = (h_1, h_1 u_1, h_2, h_2 u_2)^T$. Hereafter the density ratio, ρ_1/ρ_2 , will be denoted with r . The terms, $g h_1 \partial_x h_2$ and $r g h_2 \partial_x h_1$, represent the pressure coupling between the layers, and cause the PDE system, (1), to be non-conservative. Moreover, the non-conservative terms prevent the definition of weak solutions in the classical sense (e.g. Toro, 2013), so that the introduction of physically admissible paths connecting the states of the Riemann problem becomes necessary (Dal Maso et al. 1995; Parés, 2006).

Fig. 1. Sketch of the two-layer model over an irregular bed topography.

The conservative part of (1) yields the following flux vector

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{q}) = \left(q_2, \frac{1}{2} g q_1^2 + \frac{q_2^2}{q_1}, q_4, \frac{1}{2} g q_3^2 + \frac{q_4^2}{q_3} \right)^T. \quad (2)$$

By rewriting (1) in the quasi-linear form

$$\partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}, \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{s} = (0, -gh_1 \partial_x b, 0, -gh_2 \partial_x b)^T$, the non-conservative matrix, $\mathbf{A}_{non-cons}$, is incorporated into the pseudo-Jacobian matrix \mathbf{A} ,

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}, r) = \partial_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{A}_{non-cons} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ gq_1 - q_2^2/q_1^2 & 2q_2/q_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & gq_3 - q_4^2/q_3^2 & 2q_4/q_3 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & gq_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ rgq_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

One may be tempted to regard the non-conservative terms, $\mathbf{A}_{non-cons} \partial_x \mathbf{q}$, as source terms and neglect them in the study of the system eigenstructure. However, neglecting the non-conservative terms may cause incorrect characteristic speeds under infinitesimal perturbations at both the free surface (barotropic speeds) and the layers' interface (baroclinic speeds). As an example, for $u_1 = u_2 = u$ and $\rho_1 = \rho_2$, disregarding the non-conservative terms yields wrong barotropic speeds, $u \pm \sqrt{gh_1}$, which are smaller than the ones predicted by the classical shallow-water model, $u \pm \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)}$. The correct perturbation speeds for the two-layer model correspond to the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , i.e. to the roots of the characteristic polynomial

$$p(\mathbf{A}) = \det(\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) = (\lambda^2 - 2\lambda u_1 + u_1^2 - gh_1)(\lambda^2 - 2\lambda u_2 + u_2^2 - gh_2) - r g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0. \quad (5)$$

The PDE system (3) is non-strictly hyperbolic, since the baroclinic eigenvalues may become complex. It typically occurs if the relative velocity, $|u_1 - u_2|$, becomes sufficiently large so that Kelvin-Helmholtz type instabilities are triggered at the internal interface. In a linear model this occurrence would cause catastrophic Hadamard instabilities, which are characterized by unbounded growth rates of the short-wave perturbations (e.g. Joseph and Saut, 1990). However, in the two-layer model such instabilities are somehow less catastrophic, because the amplitudes of the perturbations saturate (thanks to non-linear effects) and high frequency terms rapidly decay (thanks to energy dissipation of shocks and other explicit dissipative mechanisms, see e.g. Keyfitz, 2003). From the viewpoint of physics these non-linear effects are associated with the onset of an intermediate mixing layer of finite thickness, which a two-layer approach is unable to describe. The aforementioned hyperbolicity loss may cause relevant numerical issues, which typically show up as unphysical oscillations of the solution if the mesh is refined (e.g. Greco et al., 2008; Castro et al., 2011).

A physics-based way to overcome these numerical issues, without the need to shift to a more complex model, is the local introduction of an additional momentum exchange, F_{extra} , for roughly capturing the effects of the turbulent-like mixing between the layers (Castro et al., 2011). Namely, the momentum equations of the PDE system (1) are slightly modified as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t (h_1 u_1) + \partial_x \left(\frac{1}{2} g h_1^2 + h_1 u_1^2 \right) + g h_1 \partial_x h_2 &= -g h_1 \partial_x b - F_{extra} \operatorname{sgn}(u_1 - u_2), \\ \partial_t (h_2 u_2) + \partial_x \left(\frac{1}{2} g h_2^2 + h_2 u_2^2 \right) + r g h_2 \partial_x h_1 &= -g h_2 \partial_x b + r F_{extra} \operatorname{sgn}(u_1 - u_2). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

If, as usual, F_{extra} cannot be estimated on a physical basis, the amount of F_{extra} has to be sufficient to keep the solution within the hyperbolic region. This amount may be calculated by an approximate formula (Castro et al., 2011) or by a more accurate and, yet more computationally demanding, iterative algorithm based on the study of the system hyperbolicity (Sarno et al., 2017). To check the system hyperbolicity for a particular solution, \mathbf{q} , several approaches are possible. One of them is to numerically calculate the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}, r)$. Yet, this method is rather time-consuming and requires the tedious calculation of the entire eigenvalues' set, which is unnecessary if the chosen numerical scheme is based on an incomplete-Riemann or Riemann-free solver.

2.1. The discriminant method

A more computationally appealing alternative is to check the hyperbolicity by calculating the discriminant, D , of the characteristic polynomial, (5). Since two of the four roots are always real, the other two ones are real if and only if $D(p(\mathbf{A})) \geq 0$ (e.g. Dickenstein and Emir, 2005). A general

analytical formula for the discriminant of a n -degree polynomial, $f(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$, reads

$$D(f) = (-1)^{\frac{1}{2}n(n-1)} \frac{1}{a_n} \det(\mathbf{R}(f, f')), \tag{7}$$

where, f' is the first derivative of f and $\mathbf{R}(f, f')$ is the Sylvester matrix of f and f' . For a quartic polynomial ($n=4$), (7) is recast as

$$D(f) = 256a_4^3 a_0^3 - 192a_4^2 a_3^1 a_1^2 a_0^2 - 128a_4^2 a_2^2 a_0^2 + 144a_4^2 a_2^1 a_2^2 a_0^1 - 27a_4^2 a_1^4 + 144a_4^1 a_3^2 a_2^1 a_0^2 - 6a_4^1 a_3^2 a_1^2 a_0^1 - 80a_4^1 a_3^1 a_2^2 a_1^1 a_0^1 + 18a_4^1 a_3^1 a_2^1 a_2^2 a_1^1 + 16a_4^1 a_2^4 a_0^1 - 4a_4^1 a_2^3 a_1^2 - 27a_3^4 a_0^2 + 18a_3^3 a_2^1 a_1^1 a_0^1 - 4a_3^3 a_1^3 - 4a_3^2 a_2^3 a_0^1 + a_3^2 a_2^2 a_1^2. \tag{8}$$

Eq. (8) was proposed by Sarno et al. (2017) to check the stability of the two-layer model and it has been found to be approximately four times faster than the numerical calculation of the eigenvalues. Performance comparison tests have been carried out in MATLAB, by confronting the computation time of (8) with the one of the *eig* built-in MATLAB function. Although (8) is an analytical exact expression, we found that relevant cancellation errors may occur, when fixed-precision variables are employed and the coefficients in (8) spread over several orders of magnitude. Unfortunately, it may occasionally happen also in cases of practical interest, i.e. when the layers' velocities are relatively large. E.g., for the values $h_1 = h_2 = 0.1$ m, $u_1 = 16$ m/s, $u_2 = 15$ m/s, $r = 0.5$ and $g = 9.806$ m/s², the formula (8) with a standard double precision floating-point format (64bit) wrongly yields a non-hyperbolic state ($D < 0$). A computationally more efficient reformulation of (8), which also greatly reduces the round-off errors, is reported by Kravavika et al. (2018)

$$D(f) = \frac{4(a_2^2 + 12a_0 - 3a_3 a_1)^3 - (27a_3^2 a_0 - 9a_3 a_2 a_1 + 2a_2^3 - 72a_2 a_0 + 27a_1^2)^2}{27}. \tag{9}$$

Eq. (9) was derived from the Ferrari's analytical solution of the quartic equation, which is based on the solution of the cubic resolvent equation by the Cardano's method (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1965). It can be easily verified that (8) is equivalent to (9), after normalizing $a_4 = 1$. Kravavika et al. (2018) reported that cancellation errors of the Ferrari's analytical solution are typically not an issue for realistic values of layers' thicknesses (0-100m) and velocities between -20 and 20 m/s. Yet, we found that (9) may still yield wrong information about the system hyperbolicity for cases with small layers' thicknesses (typically <0.01m) and large layers' velocities (>15m/s). These numerical issues can be overcome by adopting arbitrary-precision instead of double-precision arithmetic but it would cause increased computation time and implementation difficulties in some programming environments.

Moreover, it is unfortunate that the discriminant method does not allow a genuine understanding of the stability problem in terms of interplay of the involved variables. That is, it does not provide explicit information about the deviation of the solution from the hyperbolic/non-hyperbolic boundary. Hence, if the discriminant is employed to check the system hyperbolicity, an iterative algorithm is required to determine the proper amount of F_{extra} (Sarno et al., 2017).

2.2. Approximate formulae to check the system hyperbolicity

A different approach to check the model stability is by means of an approximate criterion. The classical approximate formula for Boussinesq flows (Schijf and Schönfled, 1953)

$$\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^2}{g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2)} \leq 1, \tag{10}$$

was proposed by Castro et al. (2011) to verify the model hyperbolicity and to directly calculate F_{extra} . Yet, the condition (10) is only accurate for $(1-r) \approx 0$. As an example, in Fig. 2 we report the approximate hyperbolic/non-hyperbolic boundary predicted by (10), and a number of hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic states, numerically calculated in correspondence to random values of $(h_1, h_1 u_1, h_2, h_2 u_2)^T$ with density ratios $r=0.95$, $r=0.5$ and $r=0.2$. Two different hyperbolic regions exist (in green color in Fig. 2). In geophysical flows only the left hyperbolic region is of physical interest, since these flows are typically driven by gravity from a state of rest with non-vanishing depths (Castro et al., 2011). The right hyperbolic region could become relevant in industrial and astrophysical contexts, if the initial velocities were non-zero. For $r=0.95$ (Fig. 2(a)) the approximate stability condition (10) well describes the boundary of left hyperbolic region, while it becomes progressively inaccurate, as the density ratio decreases (Fig. 2(b-c)).

Fig. 2 also reveals that the boundaries of the non-hyperbolic region become fuzzy for small enough values of r (Fig. 2(b-c)). As highlighted by Sarno et al. (2017), this scatter only shows up in the plot $|u_1 - u_2|$ vs $(h_1 + h_2)$, while the boundaries of the hyperbolic regions are sharp in the space of $(h_1, h_1 u_1, h_2, h_2 u_2)^T$. Such a behavior is caused by the fact that states with the same value of $h_1 + h_2$ may represent different thickness differences between the layers, on which the stability also depends (see e.g. Lawrence, 1990). Namely, the intermediate fuzzy regions, whose extensions grow with $(1-r)$, correspond to states that may be either hyperbolic or non-hyperbolic, depending on the relative thickness of the layers. Conversely, the uniformly colored areas in Fig. 2 correspond to states that are hyperbolic or non-hyperbolic independent from the relative thickness.

3. Asymptotic analyses

To get a deeper understanding of the stability conditions in the two-layer model, here we report different asymptotic analyses on the eigenstructure of (3). All the factors, on which the stability depends (i.e. velocity, density and layers' thickness differences), are methodically investigated. The first analysis, reported in Sec. 3.1, is based on the classical assumption of small velocity differences between the layers. The asymptotic expansions for the special cases $r = 0$ and $r = 1$ are discussed in Sec. 3.1, while the relevant case $r \rightarrow 1^-$ is reported separately in Sec. 3.1.1. A second group of asymptotic analyses is carried out assuming that the thicknesses of the layers, h_1 and h_2 , are either comparable, $|h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2) \ll 1$ (Sec. 3.2), or very different from each other, $1 - |h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2) \ll 1$ (Sec. 3.3).

3.1. Asymptotic analysis for small velocity differences

Here we study the eigenstructure of the characteristic equation, (5), associated with the PDE system (3), by assuming that the velocity difference between the layers is small. The cases of $r = 0$, $r = 1$ and $r \rightarrow 1^-$ are investigated as special cases. We define the asymptotic parameter $\epsilon =$

Fig. 2. Hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic states of the two-layer model represented in the $|u_1 - u_2| - (h_1 + h_2)$ plane, together with the approximate stability condition (10). (a) $r=0.95$, (b) $r=0.5$, (c) $r=0.2$.

$(u_1 - u_2)/u_m$, with u_m being some non-zero characteristic velocity, and assume that $|\epsilon| = |u_1 - u_2|/u_m \ll 1$. The solution of the eigenvalue problem can be approximated by an asymptotic expansion $\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1\epsilon + \lambda_2\epsilon^2 + \dots + \lambda_n\epsilon^n + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^{n+1})$. After substituting $u_2 = u_1 - \epsilon u_m$, Eq. (5) is recast as

$$(\lambda^2 - 2\lambda u_1 - g h_1 + u_1^2)(\lambda^2 - 2\lambda(u_1 - \epsilon u_m) - g h_2 + (u_1 - \epsilon u_m)^2) - r g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0. \quad (11)$$

Substituting the expansion $\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1\epsilon + \lambda_2\epsilon^2 + \dots$ in (11) and neglecting higher order terms, the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -equation is

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0 u_1 - g h_1 + u_1^2)(\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0 u_1 - g h_2 + u_1^2) - r g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0. \quad (12)$$

Eq. (12) is biquadratic in $(\lambda_0 - u_1)$. Hence, the roots are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_0^{(1)} &= u_1 + \sqrt{\frac{g}{2} \left[(h_1 + h_2) + \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1 h_2} \right]}, & \lambda_0^{(2)} &= u_1 - \sqrt{\frac{g}{2} \left[(h_1 + h_2) + \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1 h_2} \right]} \\ \lambda_0^{(3)} &= u_1 + \sqrt{\frac{g}{2} \left[(h_1 + h_2) - \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1 h_2} \right]}, & \lambda_0^{(4)} &= u_1 - \sqrt{\frac{g}{2} \left[(h_1 + h_2) - \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1 h_2} \right]}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

It can be easily verified that λ_0 in (13) are real for $0 \leq r \leq 1$. In the limiting case $r = 0$ (i.e. zero pressure coupling between layers), (13) yields $\lambda_0^{(1,2)} = u_1 \pm \sqrt{gh_1}$ and $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1 \pm \sqrt{gh_2}$, which match the eigenvalues of the shallow water model, written separately for the two layers. In the other limiting case $r = 1$, $\lambda_0^{(1,2)} = u_1 \pm \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)}$ and $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$, where the barotropic speeds match the eigenvalues of the shallow water model written for the entire current. The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation, obtained from (11) by collecting $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ terms, reads

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_1)(2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1 + 2u_m\lambda_0 - 2u_1u_m) + (\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_2)(2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1) = 0, \tag{14}$$

whence

$$\lambda_1 = -\frac{u_m(\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 - gh_1 + u_1^2)(\lambda_0 - u_1)}{(2\lambda_0^2 - 4u_1\lambda_0 + 2u_1^2 - gh_2 - gh_1)(\lambda_0 - u_1)}. \tag{15}$$

By substituting $\lambda_0^{(1)}, \lambda_0^{(2)}, \lambda_0^{(3)}, \lambda_0^{(4)}$ into (15), the four $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -coefficients, $\lambda_1^{(1)}, \lambda_1^{(2)}, \lambda_1^{(3)}, \lambda_1^{(4)}$, are

$$\lambda_1^{(1,2)} = \frac{u_m \left[(h_1 - h_2) - \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1h_2} \right]}{2\sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1h_2}}, \quad \lambda_1^{(3,4)} = \frac{u_m \left[(h_2 - h_1) - \sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1h_2} \right]}{2\sqrt{(h_1 + h_2)^2 - 4(1-r)h_1h_2}}. \tag{16}$$

If $r = 0$, $\lambda_1^{(1,2)} = 0$ and $\lambda_1^{(3,4)} = -u_m$. Conversely, if $r = 1$, $\lambda_1^{(1,2)} = -\frac{h_2u_m}{h_1+h_2}$, while $\lambda_1^{(3,4)}$ are indeterminate because Eq. (14) is identically satisfied for $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$.

The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation is

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_1)(2\lambda_0\lambda_2 - 2u_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_1^2 + 2u_m\lambda_1 + u_m^2) + (\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_2)(2\lambda_0\lambda_2 - 2u_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_1^2) + (2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1)(2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1 + 2u_m\lambda_0 - 2u_1u_m) = 0, \tag{17}$$

whence

$$\lambda_2 = -\frac{(6\lambda_0^2 - 12u_1\lambda_0 + 6u_1^2 - gh_2 - gh_1)\lambda_1^2 + [6\lambda_0^2 - 12u_1\lambda_0 + (6u_1^2 - 2gh_1)]u_m\lambda_1 + u_m^2\lambda_0(\lambda_0 - 2u_1) + (u_1^2 - gh_1)u_m^2}{4\lambda_0^3 - 12u_1\lambda_0^2 + (12u_1^2 - 2gh_2 - 2gh_1)\lambda_0 - 4u_1^3 + (2gh_2 + 2gh_1)u_1}. \tag{18}$$

By substituting $\lambda_0^{(1,2,3,4)}$ and $\lambda_1^{(1,2,3,4)}$ into (18), the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -coefficients, $\lambda_2^{(1)}, \lambda_2^{(2)}, \lambda_2^{(3)}, \lambda_2^{(4)}$, are obtained. If $r = 0$, the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -coefficients are

$$\lambda_2^{(1)} = \frac{h_2u_m^2(4h_1^2 - h_1h_2 + h_2^2)}{2\sqrt{gh_1}(h_1+h_2)^2(h_1-h_2)}, \quad \lambda_2^{(2)} = -\lambda_2^{(1)}, \tag{19}$$

$$\lambda_2^{(3)} = -\frac{h_1u_m^2(h_1^2 - h_1h_2 + 4h_2^2)}{2\sqrt{gh_2}(h_1+h_2)^2(h_1-h_2)}, \quad \lambda_2^{(4)} = -\lambda_2^{(3)}.$$

Conversely, if $r = 1$, Eq. (17) yields

$$\lambda_2^{(1)} = \frac{3h_1h_2u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1+h_2)^{5/2}}, \quad \lambda_2^{(2)} = -\frac{3h_1h_2u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1+h_2)^{5/2}}, \quad \lambda_2^{(3)} \text{ and } \lambda_2^{(4)} \text{ indeterminate.} \tag{20}$$

After substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$ into Eq. (17), the following equation determining the still unknown $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -coefficients, $\lambda_1^{(3)}$ and $\lambda_1^{(4)}$, emerges

$$-gh_1(\lambda_1^2 + 2u_m\lambda_1 + u_m^2) - gh_2\lambda_1^2 = 0, \tag{21}$$

whence

$$\lambda_1^{(3)} = \frac{[-h_1 + i(\sqrt{h_1h_2})]u_m}{h_1 + h_2}, \quad \lambda_1^{(4)} = \frac{[-h_1 - i(\sqrt{h_1h_2})]u_m}{h_1 + h_2}. \tag{22}$$

For $r=1$, Eq. (17) cannot determine $\lambda_2^{(3)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(4)}$. Hence, we need to study the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$ -equation,

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_1)(2\lambda_0\lambda_3 - 2u_1\lambda_3 + 2\lambda_1\lambda_2 + 2u_m\lambda_2) + (\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1\lambda_0 + u_1^2 - gh_2)(2\lambda_0\lambda_3 - 2u_1\lambda_3 + 2\lambda_1\lambda_2) + (2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1)(2\lambda_0\lambda_2 - 2u_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_1^2 + 2u_m\lambda_1 + u_m^2) + (2\lambda_0\lambda_1 - 2u_1\lambda_1 + 2u_m\lambda_0 - 2u_1u_m)(2\lambda_0\lambda_2 - 2u_1\lambda_2) = 0. \tag{23}$$

Substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$ and $\lambda_1 = \lambda_1^{(3,4)}$ of (22) into Eq. (23), we get

$$-gh_1(2\lambda_1\lambda_2 + 2u_m\lambda_2) - 2gh_2\lambda_1\lambda_2 = 0, \tag{24}$$

which results in $\lambda_2^{(3,4)} = 0$. In summary, for $r = 1$, the second order expansions of the PDE system eigenvalues are

$$\lambda^{(1)} = \lambda_0^{(1)} + \lambda_1^{(1)}\epsilon^1 + \lambda_2^{(1)}\epsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3) = \frac{h_1u_1 + h_2u_2}{h_1 + h_2} + \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)} + \frac{3h_1h_2(u_1 - u_2)^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right), \tag{25}$$

$$\lambda^{(2)} = \frac{h_1u_1 + h_2u_2}{h_1 + h_2} - \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)} - \frac{3h_1h_2(u_1 - u_2)^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right), \tag{26}$$

$$\lambda^{(3)} = \frac{h_1u_2 + h_2u_1}{h_1 + h_2} + i\frac{(u_1 - u_2)}{2}\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{h_1 - h_2}{h_1 + h_2}\right)^2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right), \tag{27}$$

$$\lambda^{(4)} = \frac{h_1 u_2 + h_2 u_1}{h_1 + h_2} - i \frac{(u_1 - u_2)}{2} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{h_1 - h_2}{h_1 + h_2}\right)^2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right), \tag{28}$$

where $\lambda^{(1,2)}$ and $\lambda^{(3,4)}$ are the barotropic and baroclinic speeds, respectively. The first-order truncations of (25)-(26)-(27)-(28) recover the approximations reported by Audusse (2005) for layered flows of uniform density. For $r = 1$, it is worth remarking that any non-zero velocity difference between the layers immediately causes the loss of hyperbolicity. The modulus of the imaginary parts of $\lambda^{(3,4)}$ is bounded by $|u_1 - u_2|/2$ and depends on the factor $\sqrt{1 - [(h_1 - h_2)/(h_1 + h_2)]^2} \leq 1$. Note that, beside the case $|u_1 - u_2| \rightarrow 0$, the system is asymptotically stable, even if one layer thickness becomes negligible compared to the other ($|h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2) \rightarrow 1^-$). The importance of the quantity, $\kappa = |h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2)$, hereafter referred to as *relative thickness difference*, confirms that the source of instability, due to $r=1$ and a non-zero velocity difference, ultimately depends on the pressure coupling between the layers, and, thus, to be effective, requires that the layers thicknesses are non-negligible with respect to each other. The degenerate hyperbolic region is given by the criterion

$$(u_1 - u_2)^2(1 - \kappa) \rightarrow 0. \tag{29}$$

3.1.1. Special case: $r = 1 - \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^\alpha)$

Here, we assume that r is slightly smaller than 1, with $(1 - r) = \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^\alpha)$ ($\alpha \leq 2$). The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -equation, (12), is, thus, recast as

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0 u_1 - g h_1 + u_1^2)(\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0 u_1 - g h_2 + u_1^2) - g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0, \tag{30}$$

and admits the same roots, $\lambda_0^{(1,2)} = u_1 \pm \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)}$, $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$, already found for $r = 1$. The remaining part of $-rg^2 h_1 h_2$, i.e. the term $(1 - r)g^2 h_1 h_2$ cannot be accounted for in the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation, since the modified $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation would have no solutions for the two baroclinic branches (i.e. with $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$ we would get $(1 - r)/\epsilon \cdot g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0$). Thus, from the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation we get the same roots of $r = 1$. Conversely, the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation, (17), is rewritten as follows,

$$(\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1 \lambda_0 + u_1^2 - g h_1)(2\lambda_0 \lambda_2 - 2u_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_1^2 + 2u_m \lambda_1 + u_m^2) + (\lambda_0^2 - 2u_1 \lambda_0 + u_1^2 - g h_2)(2\lambda_0 \lambda_2 - 2u_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_1^2) + (2\lambda_0 \lambda_1 - 2u_1 \lambda_1)(2\lambda_0 \lambda_1 - 2u_1 \lambda_1 + 2u_m \lambda_0 - 2u_1 u_m) + \frac{1-r}{\epsilon^2} g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0. \tag{31}$$

The barotropic roots, $\lambda_2^{(1)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(2)}$, are slightly different than the ones from (20)

$$\lambda_2^{(1)} = \frac{3h_1 h_2 u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} - \frac{g(1-r)h_1 h_2 (h_1 + h_2) u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2} (u_1 - u_2)^2}, \quad \lambda_2^{(2)} = -\frac{3h_1 h_2 u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} + \frac{g(1-r)h_1 h_2 (h_1 + h_2) u_m^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2} (u_1 - u_2)^2}, \tag{32}$$

while $\lambda_2^{(3,4)}$ are indeterminate, analogous to that found with (20). Indeed, after substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$ into (31), we get

$$-g h_1 (\lambda_1^2 + 2u_m \lambda_1 + u_m^2) - g h_2 \lambda_1^2 + \frac{1-r}{\epsilon^2} g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0, \tag{33}$$

which, substituting $\epsilon = (u_1 - u_2)/u_m$, is recast as

$$-g h_1 (\lambda_1^2 + 2u_m \lambda_1 + u_m^2) - g h_2 \lambda_1^2 + \frac{1-r}{(u_1 - u_2)^2} u_m^2 g^2 h_1 h_2 = 0. \tag{34}$$

Eq. (34) allows to determine the still unknown first-order baroclinic coefficients,

$$\lambda_1^{(3)} = \frac{u_m \left\{ h_1 (u_1 - u_2) + \sqrt{h_1 h_2 [g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2) - (u_1 - u_2)^2]} \right\}}{(h_1 + h_2)(u_2 - u_1)}, \tag{35}$$

$$\lambda_1^{(4)} = \frac{u_m \left\{ h_1 (u_1 - u_2) - \sqrt{h_1 h_2 [g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2) - (u_1 - u_2)^2]} \right\}}{(h_1 + h_2)(u_2 - u_1)}.$$

$\lambda_1^{(3,4)}$ are real numbers if and only if

$$g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2) - (u_1 - u_2)^2 \geq 0. \tag{36}$$

The stability condition (36), here derived under the hypothesis that $r = 1 - \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^\alpha)$, recovers the approximate criterion, (10). Different from the case with $r=1$, the hyperbolic domain is not degenerate. Yet, only the left hyperbolic region (cf. Fig. 2) is predicted by (36), since this condition is still based on the assumption of small velocity differences. Moreover, it is interesting to note that, different from the stability criterion (29), (36) depends on the quantities, $(1 - r)$, $(h_1 + h_2)$, $|u_1 - u_2|$, but not on $\kappa = |h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2)$. It indicates that κ is not critical for the stability, if r is smaller but close to 1. Nonetheless, we anticipate (cf. Sec. 3.4) that, beyond the range of validity of Cond. (36), some effects of κ on the stability arise, similar to that already observed in Cond. (29).

Finally, to determine $\lambda_2^{(3)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(4)}$, we use the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$ -equation, (23), which is unchanged. Substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)} = u_1$ and the expressions of $\lambda_1^{(3,4)}$, reported in (35), into (23), it can be checked that, also in this case, $\lambda_2^{(3,4)} = 0$.

The expansions of the eigenvalues up to $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ for $r = 1 - \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^\alpha)$ are summarized below

$$\lambda^{(1,2)} = \lambda_0^{(1,2)} + \lambda_1^{(1,2)} \epsilon + \lambda_2^{(1,2)} \epsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3) \tag{37}$$

$$= \frac{h_1 u_1 + h_2 u_2}{h_1 + h_2} \pm \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)} \pm \frac{3h_1 h_2 (u_1 - u_2)^2}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} \mp \frac{g(1-r)h_1 h_2 (h_1 + h_2)}{2\sqrt{g}(h_1 + h_2)^{5/2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right),$$

$$\lambda^{(3,4)} = \frac{h_2 u_1 + h_1 u_2}{h_1 + h_2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{g(1-r)h_1 h_2}{h_1 + h_2} - \frac{(u_1 - u_2)^2 h_1 h_2}{(h_1 + h_2)^2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(u_1 - u_2)^3}{u_m^3}\right). \tag{38}$$

By truncating (37)-(38) at the first order, we recover the classical formulae by Schijf and Schönfeld (1953).

3.2. Asymptotic analysis for layers of comparable thicknesses

Here, we perform a different asymptotic analysis, by assuming that the layers' thicknesses are comparable. Namely we introduce the alternative asymptotic parameter $\epsilon = (h_2 - h_1)/(h_1 + h_2)$ with $|\epsilon| < \ll 1$. Thus, the layers' thicknesses are expressed as $h_1 = \bar{h} - \epsilon\bar{h}$ and $h_2 = \bar{h} + \epsilon\bar{h}$, with $\bar{h} = (h_1 + h_2)/2$. Without loss of generality, the layers' velocities can be written as $u_1 = \bar{u} + \Delta u/2$ and $u_2 = \bar{u} - \Delta u/2$, with $\bar{u} = (u_1 + u_2)/2$ and $\Delta u = u_1 - u_2$. Therefore, Eq. (5) is recast as

$$\left[\lambda^2 - 2\lambda\left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g(\bar{h} - \epsilon\bar{h}) \right] \cdot \left[\lambda^2 - 2\lambda\left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g(\bar{h} + \epsilon\bar{h}) \right] - rg^2(\bar{h} - \epsilon\bar{h})(\bar{h} + \epsilon\bar{h}) = 0 \quad (39)$$

Substituting $\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1\epsilon + \lambda_2\epsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$ into (39), the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -equation is

$$\left[\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0\left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g\bar{h} \right] \left[\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0\left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g\bar{h} \right] - rg^2\bar{h}^2 = 0. \quad (40)$$

Although less obvious than the case of Eq. (12), also (40) is a biquadratic equation. Indeed, introducing the variable $\zeta = (\lambda_0 - \bar{u})^2$, (40) is recast as

$$\zeta^2 + \left(-2g\bar{h} - \frac{1}{2}\Delta u^2\right)\zeta + g^2\bar{h}^2(1-r) + \Delta u^2\left(\frac{1}{16}\Delta u^2 - \frac{1}{2}g\bar{h}\right) = 0, \quad (41)$$

which yields the solutions

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_0^{(1)} &= \bar{u} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(\Delta u^2 + rg\bar{h})}}, \\ \lambda_0^{(2)} &= \bar{u} - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(\Delta u^2 + rg\bar{h})}}, \\ \lambda_0^{(3)} &= \bar{u} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(\Delta u^2 + rg\bar{h})}}, \\ \lambda_0^{(4)} &= \bar{u} - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(\Delta u^2 + rg\bar{h})}}, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where the superscripts (1,2) and (3,4), respectively, stand for the barotropic and baroclinic branches. While $\lambda_0^{(1,2)}$ are always real, $\lambda_0^{(3,4)}$ are real if and only if

$$\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} \geq 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(\Delta u^2 + rg\bar{h})}. \quad (43)$$

The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation, associated with (39) is

$$(4\lambda_0^3 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 4\bar{u}^3 + (4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)\bar{u})\lambda_1 - 2\Delta ug\bar{h}\lambda_0 + 2\Delta ug\bar{h}\bar{u} = 0. \quad (44)$$

Its solution takes the form

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{2\Delta ug\bar{h}(\lambda_0 - \bar{u})}{(4\lambda_0^3 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 4\bar{u}^3 + (4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)\bar{u})}. \quad (45)$$

Substituting the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -solutions, $\lambda_0^{(1,2,3,4)}$, into (45), we obtain

$$\lambda_1^{(1,2)} = \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}, \quad \lambda_1^{(3,4)} = -\frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}. \quad (46)$$

The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation is obtained from (39)

$$\begin{aligned} (8\lambda_0^3 - 24\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (24\bar{u}^2 - 8g\bar{h} - 2\Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 8\bar{u}^3 + (8g\bar{h} + 2\Delta u^2)\bar{u})\lambda_2 + \\ (12\lambda_0^2 - 24\bar{u}\lambda_0 + 12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_1^2 - 4\Delta ug\bar{h}\lambda_1 + 2g^2\bar{h}^2r - 2g^2\bar{h}^2 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

whence

$$\lambda_2 = \frac{(12\lambda_0^2 - 24\bar{u}\lambda_0 + 12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_1^2 - 4\Delta ug\bar{h}\lambda_1 + 2g^2\bar{h}^2r - 2g^2\bar{h}^2}{8\lambda_0^3 - 24\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (24\bar{u}^2 - 8g\bar{h} - 2\Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 8\bar{u}^3 + (8g\bar{h} + 2\Delta u^2)\bar{u}}. \quad (48)$$

Substituting the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ and $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ coefficients into (47), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_2^{(1)} &= \frac{-\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}\left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2\right] - 2\Delta u^2g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2\sqrt{4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}, \\ \lambda_2^{(2)} &= -\lambda_2^{(1)}, \\ \lambda_2^{(3)} &= \frac{\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}\left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2\right] - 2\Delta u^2g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2\sqrt{4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}, \\ \lambda_2^{(4)} &= -\lambda_2^{(3)}. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

In summary, the asymptotic expansions up to the second order are put together below

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^{(1)} &= \frac{u_1 + u_2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} + \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}\left[\frac{h_2 - h_1}{h_1 + h_2}\right]^1 \\ &+ \frac{-\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}\left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2\right] - 2\Delta u^2g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2\sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}}\left[\frac{h_2 - h_1}{h_1 + h_2}\right]^2 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(h_2 - h_1)^3}{(h_1 + h_2)^3}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

$$\lambda^{(2)} = \frac{u_1+u_2}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} + \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^1 + \frac{\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)} \left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2 \right] + 2\Delta u^2 g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} + 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^2 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(h_2-h_1)^3}{(h_1+h_2)^3}\right), \tag{51}$$

$$\lambda^{(3)} = \frac{u_1+u_2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} - \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^1 + \frac{\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)} \left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2 \right] - 2\Delta u^2 g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^2 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(h_2-h_1)^3}{(h_1+h_2)^3}\right), \tag{52}$$

$$\lambda^{(4)} = \frac{u_1+u_2}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} - \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}}{2\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^1 + \frac{-\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)} \left[(2rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 - 4rg^2\bar{h}^2 \right] + 2\Delta u^2 g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}{8(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)^2 \sqrt{\Delta u^2 + 4g\bar{h} - 4\sqrt{g\bar{h}(rg\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)}}} \left[\frac{h_2-h_1}{h_1+h_2} \right]^2 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(h_2-h_1)^3}{(h_1+h_2)^3}\right). \tag{53}$$

3.2.1. Stability criterion for layers of comparable thicknesses

The above asymptotic expansions, carried out for $\kappa = |h_2 - h_1|/(h_1 + h_2) \ll 1$, may yield two complex eigenvalues, as $\lambda_0^{(3,4)}$ may become complex. Conversely, λ_1 and λ_2 are always real for all branches of the solution. As the dominant imaginary parts of $\lambda^{(3,4)}$ are given by the corresponding $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -coefficients, the inequality, (43), can be regarded as a criterion for the PDE system hyperbolicity, which is exact for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$. After some algebraic manipulations, (43) is recast as

$$\frac{g^2(1-r)(h_1 + h_2)^2}{\Delta u^2} - g(h_1 + h_2) + \frac{\Delta u^2}{4} \geq 0. \tag{54}$$

It is interesting to compare Cond. (54) with (36), derived under the hypotheses of $|\Delta u| \rightarrow 0$ and $r \rightarrow 1$. The two conditions show a similar structure with the only difference being represented by the term $\Delta u^2/4$, which has a stabilizing effect. For $|\Delta u| \rightarrow 0$, Cond. (54) recovers the stability criterion (36). Thanks to the quadratic term Δu^2 , (54) describes two separate hyperbolic regions and, thus, is also capable of capturing the right hyperbolic region (cf. Fig. 2). Please note that the left-hand side of (54) is a second degree polynomial in the two variables $(h_1 + h_2)$ and Δu^2 and, hence, it can be easily factorized. Consequently, (54) is decomposed into the following two conditions

$$\Delta u^2 - 2g(1 - \sqrt{r})(h_1 + h_2) \leq 0, \tag{55}$$

$$\Delta u^2 - 2g(1 + \sqrt{r})(h_1 + h_2) \geq 0, \tag{56}$$

which respectively correspond to the left and right hyperbolic domains. For $(1 - r) \rightarrow 0$, thus $2(1 - \sqrt{r}) \approx 1 - r$: hence the leading order approximation of (55) recovers the stability criterion, (36). This remarkable correspondence between the two stability criteria also explains why, in the limit of $(1 - r) \rightarrow 0$, the classical criterion, (36), gives a reasonably good estimation of the hyperbolic boundary even for large values of $|\Delta u|$ (cf. Fig. 2(a)). For $r=0$ (55)-(56) are alternatively verified for any flow condition, as the middle non-hyperbolic region vanishes.

3.3. Asymptotic analysis for the limiting case of very large thickness difference

Finally, we perform the asymptotic analysis for $\kappa \rightarrow 1$. We assume that $h_2 \gg h_1$ and, thus, $(h_2 - h_1)/(h_1 + h_2) \rightarrow 1^-$. However, note that Eq. (5) is symmetric with respect to the layers' indices, hence the choice of $h_2 \gg h_1$ is irrelevant in this analysis. Here we define the asymptotic parameter as $\epsilon = 1 - (h_2 - h_1)/(h_1 + h_2) \rightarrow 0^+$. Hence, the layers' thicknesses are $h_1 = \epsilon\bar{h}$ and $h_2 = (2 - \epsilon)\bar{h}$, with $\bar{h} = (h_1 + h_2)/2$. As in Sec. 3.2, we use the notation $u_1 = \bar{u} + \Delta u/2$, $u_2 = \bar{u} - \Delta u/2$, with $\bar{u} = (u_1 + u_2)/2$ and $\Delta u = u_1 - u_2$. Eq. (5) is recast as

$$\left[\lambda^2 - 2\lambda\left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g\epsilon\bar{h} \right] \cdot \left[\lambda^2 - 2\lambda\left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - g\bar{h}(2 - \epsilon) \right] - rg^2\bar{h}^2(2 - \epsilon)\epsilon = 0. \tag{57}$$

The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^0)$ -equation is

$$\left[\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0\left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 \right] \left[\lambda_0^2 - 2\lambda_0\left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right) + \left(\bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2}\right)^2 - 2g\bar{h} \right] = 0, \tag{58}$$

whence

$$\lambda_0^{(1)} = \bar{u} - \frac{\Delta u}{2} + \sqrt{2g\bar{h}} = u_2 + \sqrt{g(h_1 + h_2)}, \quad \lambda_0^{(2)} = -\lambda_0^{(1)}, \quad \lambda_0^{(3)} = \bar{u} + \frac{\Delta u}{2} = u_1, \quad \lambda_0^{(4)} = \lambda_0^{(3)}. \tag{59}$$

The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^1)$ -equation is

$$[4\lambda_0^3 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 4\bar{u}^3 + (4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)\bar{u} + 2\Delta ug\bar{h}] \lambda_1 + 2\Delta ug\bar{h}\bar{u}(1 - \lambda_0) + 2(1 - r)g^2\bar{h}^2 = 0. \tag{60}$$

Substituting $\lambda_0^{(1,2)}$ in (60), we obtain the two barotropic coefficients

$$\lambda_1^{(1)} = \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}(\sqrt{8g\bar{h}} + \Delta u) + 2g^2\bar{h}^2(1 - r)}{\sqrt{8g\bar{h}}(2g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2) + 8\Delta ug\bar{h}}, \quad \lambda_1^{(2)} = \frac{\Delta ug\bar{h}(\sqrt{8g\bar{h}} - \Delta u) - 2g^2\bar{h}^2(1 - r)}{\sqrt{8g\bar{h}}(2g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2) - 8\Delta ug\bar{h}}. \tag{61}$$

Conversely, substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)}$ in (60), we get

$$0 \cdot \lambda_1 + 2g^2\bar{h}^2(1-r) - \Delta u^2 g\bar{h} = 0, \tag{62}$$

which does not allow to determine $\lambda_1^{(3,4)}$. Moreover, Eq. (62) is verified only for certain values of the solution. Thus, we need to take into account the non-zero remainder of the left hand side of (62) in the baroclinic branches of the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation. The $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation, valid for the barotropic branches of the solution, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & [4\lambda_0^3 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 4\bar{u}^3 + (4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)\bar{u} + 2\Delta u g\bar{h}]\lambda_2 + \\ & [6\lambda_0^2 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0 + 6\bar{u}^2 - 2g\bar{h} - (1/2)\Delta u^2]\lambda_1^2 - 2\Delta u g\bar{h}\lambda_1 + (r-1)g^2\bar{h}^2 = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

After substituting $\lambda_0^{(1,2)}$ and $\lambda_1^{(1,2)}$ into (63) we obtain the coefficients, $\lambda_2^{(1)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(2)}$ (not reported here for brevity). Differently, for the two baroclinic branches, the $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ -equation, (63), is modified with the remainder of (62), namely

$$\begin{aligned} & [4\lambda_0^3 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0^2 + (12\bar{u}^2 - 4g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_0 - 4\bar{u}^3 + (4g\bar{h} + \Delta u^2)\bar{u} + 2\Delta u g\bar{h}]\lambda_2 + \\ & [6\lambda_0^2 - 12\bar{u}\lambda_0 + 6\bar{u}^2 - 2g\bar{h} - (1/2)\Delta u^2]\lambda_1^2 - 2\Delta u g\bar{h}\lambda_1 + (r-1)g^2\bar{h}^2 + \frac{[2g^2\bar{h}^2(1-r) - \Delta u^2 g\bar{h}]}{\epsilon} = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

By substituting $\lambda_0^{(3,4)}$ into (64), we obtain the following equation in λ_1 ,

$$\epsilon(2g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)\lambda_1^2 + 2\epsilon\Delta u g\bar{h}\lambda_1 + [\epsilon - 2 + (2 - \epsilon)r]g^2\bar{h}^2 + \Delta u^2 g\bar{h} = 0, \tag{65}$$

whence

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1^{(3)} &= \frac{-2\epsilon\Delta u g\bar{h} + \sqrt{4\epsilon^2\Delta u^2 g^2\bar{h}^2 - 4\epsilon(2g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)[(\epsilon - 2 + (2 - \epsilon)r)g^2\bar{h}^2 + \Delta u^2 g\bar{h}]}}{2\epsilon(2g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)}, \\ \lambda_1^{(4)} &= \frac{-2\epsilon\Delta u g\bar{h} - \sqrt{4\epsilon^2\Delta u^2 g^2\bar{h}^2 - 4\epsilon(2g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)[(\epsilon - 2 + (2 - \epsilon)r)g^2\bar{h}^2 + \Delta u^2 g\bar{h}]}}{2\epsilon(2g\bar{h} - \Delta u^2)}. \end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

Obviously, $\lambda_1^{(3)}$ and $\lambda_1^{(4)}$ are real if and only if

$$\Delta u^4 - \Delta u^2 g(h_1 + h_2)(2-r)\left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) + g^2(h_1 + h_2)^2(1-r)\left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \geq 0. \tag{67}$$

In the limit that $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, (67) is recast as

$$\Delta u^4 - \Delta u^2 g(h_1 + h_2)(2-r) + g^2(h_1 + h_2)^2(1-r) \geq 0, \tag{68}$$

equivalent to

$$[\Delta u^2 - g(h_1 + h_2)] \cdot [\Delta u^2 - g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2)] \geq 0. \tag{69}$$

(69) can be decomposed into the following inequalities,

$$\Delta u^2 - g(1-r)(h_1 + h_2) \leq 0, \tag{70}$$

$$\Delta u^2 - g(h_1 + h_2) \geq 0. \tag{71}$$

It is interesting to note that Cond. (70) is equivalent to (36), derived with the completely different assumptions of $(1-r) \rightarrow 0$ and $|\Delta u| \rightarrow 0$. On the one hand, it suggests that, for the stability, $\kappa \rightarrow 1$ is equivalent to assuming $(1-r) \rightarrow 0$. It is reasonable considering that both factors play a similar role in the model stability through the pressure distributions within the layers. However, it should be remarked that Cond. (70) is valid for any density ratio, and, hence, it expands the range of validity of (36). Another clear advantage of the present analysis, over the previous asymptotical analysis with $|\Delta u| < 1$, is that a description of the right hyperbolic region is also provided (Cond. (71)). Comparing Cond. (70) with (55), it can be also noted that the left hyperbolic region by (70) is strictly contained in the region by (55). Thus, Conditions (55) and (70), whose difference vanishes for $r \rightarrow 1$, are lower and upper bounds for the left boundary of the non-hyperbolic region (cf. Fig. 2). Conversely, Conditions (71) and (56) represent the upper and lower bounds of the right boundary.

3.4. General stability conditions

The latter asymptotic analyses, carried out by respectively assuming small and diverging thickness differences between the layers, provided new stability criteria, (55)-(56) and (70)-(71), capable of describing both left and right hyperbolic regions. Clearly, for intermediate values of κ , the criteria (55)-(56), derived for $\kappa < 1$, and, especially, the criteria (70)-(71), derived in the sharp limit of $\kappa \rightarrow 1$, are expected to yield some errors. Yet, the analytical structures of (55)-(56) and (70)-(71) are very similar and characterized by a proportionality between Δu^2 and $(h_1 + h_2)$ through a certain factor depending on r . Thus, by keeping this analytical structure, it could be possible to derive a general stability criterion, also valid for intermediate values of κ . By assuming that the limiting conditions (55)-(56) and (70)-(71) are smoothly connected to each other by two regularization functions, $\xi_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\xi_2(\kappa, r)$, a generalized reformulation of (55)-(56) can be written in the following compact forms

$$\frac{\Delta u^2}{2g(1 - \sqrt{r})\xi_1(\kappa, r)(h_1 + h_2)} \leq 1, \tag{72}$$

$$\frac{\Delta u^2}{2g(1 + \sqrt{r})\xi_2(\kappa, r)(h_1 + h_2)} \geq 1, \tag{73}$$

where $\xi_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\xi_2(\kappa, r)$ have to fulfill the following constraints,

$$\xi_1(0, r) = 1, \quad \xi_2(0, r) = 1, \quad \xi_1(1^-, r) = \frac{(1-r)}{2(1 - \sqrt{r})}, \quad \xi_2(1^-, r) = \frac{1}{2(1 + \sqrt{r})}. \tag{74}$$

In the limiting cases of $r = 0$ and $r \rightarrow 1^-$, (74) yields

$$\xi_1(1^-, 0) = \xi_2(1^-, 0) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \xi_1(1^-, 1^-) = 1, \quad \xi_2(1^-, 1^-) = \frac{1}{4}. \tag{75}$$

Fig. 3. Hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic states in the $(u_1 - u_2)^2 - (h_1 + h_2)$ plane ($r=0.2, \kappa = 0.5$).

4. Numerical tests and approximate stability criteria

In this section, by an extensive numerical investigation, we propose suitable approximations of the functions, ξ_1 and ξ_2 , sketched in (72)-(73). Subsequently, we investigate the reliability of the various stability criteria.

4.1. Calibration of the regularization functions

The asymptotic analyses for $\kappa < 1$ and $\kappa \rightarrow 1$ indicate that the boundaries between the hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic regions may be described by a linear relationship between Δu^2 and $(h_1 + h_2)$. We numerically checked that this behavior is also verified for intermediate values of $0 < \kappa < 1$. After setting arbitrary values for κ and r , we generated 10^6 random values of $(h_1, h_1 u_1, h_2, h_2 u_2)^T$ in the ranges $0 \text{ m} < h_1 + h_2 \leq 50 \text{ m}$ and $0 \leq |u_1 - u_2| \leq 20 \text{ m/s}$. Different from the random generations reported in Fig. 2, here the layers' thicknesses h_1 and h_2 are constrained by the fixed $\kappa = |h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2)$, chosen a priori. The following values of κ and r , encompassing the entire range of flow conditions, have been investigated:

$$k \in \{0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99\}, \quad (76)$$

$$r \in \{0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99\}. \quad (77)$$

The numerical data confirm that the boundaries of the hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic regions always exhibit a linear behavior for any choice of κ and r . As an example, Fig. 3 reports the hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic states in the plane $\Delta u^2 - (h_1 + h_2)$ for the case $\kappa = 0.5$ and $r = 0.2$. From Fig. 3, it can be noted that the boundaries between hyperbolic and non-hyperbolic regions are sharp, different from Fig. 2(b). It is due to the fact that here, all states share the same κ .

By numerically tracking the linear boundaries of the non-hyperbolic region for each investigated combination of (κ, r) , we calculated the best-fitting ratios $(h_1 + h_2)/\Delta u^2$ at the boundaries. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , was found >0.99 for all investigated combinations of κ and r . Then, by exploiting (72)-(73), we obtained numerical point-wise estimations of the regularization functions, denoted as $\hat{\xi}_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\hat{\xi}_2(\kappa, r)$.

Considering the generalized stability conditions, (72)-(73), and the constraints, (74), we propose the following exponential functions for $\xi_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\xi_2(\kappa, r)$

$$\xi_1(\kappa, r) = \exp \left(\ln \left(\frac{1 - r + (1 - \kappa)^{a_1} (1 + r - 2\sqrt{r})}{2(1 - \sqrt{r})} \right) \cdot (b_1 \kappa^{c_1}) \right), \quad (78)$$

Table 1

Best-fitting parameters of the regularization functions $\xi_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\xi_2(\kappa, r)$, obtained by numerical data.

	a_i	b_i	c_i	R^2	SSE	RMSE
ξ_1	0.5690	1.0000	1.0000	0.9999	$5.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.96 \cdot 10^{-4}$
ξ_2	0.2981	1.1295	0.7597	0.9999	$1.11 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Comparisons between the best-fitting regularization functions, $\xi_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\xi_2(\kappa, r)$, (colored surface) and the discrete numerical functions $\hat{\xi}_1(\kappa, r)$ and $\hat{\xi}_2(\kappa, r)$ (black dots), respectively.

$$\xi_2(\kappa, r) = \exp \left(\ln \left(\frac{1 + (1 - \kappa)^{a_2} (1 + 2\sqrt{r})}{2(1 + \sqrt{r})} \right) \cdot (b_2 \kappa^{c_2}) \right), \quad (79)$$

where the parameters a_i, b_i , and c_i have to be calibrated on $\hat{\xi}_1$ and $\hat{\xi}_2$. Note that (78)-(79) are constructed in such a way that, for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$, the first two conditions of (74) are fulfilled in a smooth way. Conversely, for $\kappa \rightarrow 1$, (78) and (79), respectively, tend to $(1 - r)/[2(1 - \sqrt{r})]$ and $1/[2(1 + \sqrt{r})]$, as required by the other two constraints. The best-fitting values of a_i, b_i , and c_i are reported in Table 1, together with the fitness indicators R^2 (coefficient of determination), SSE (sum of squares due to error) and $RMSE$ (root mean square error). Moreover, comparisons between ξ_1 and $\hat{\xi}_1$, and between ξ_2 and $\hat{\xi}_2$ are reported in Fig. 4.

As shown in Table 1 and in Fig. 4, the agreement between the best-fitting functions, (78)-(79), and the numerical data is very good. It confirms that the choice of the simple analytical functions (78) and (79) is reasonable. More sophisticated functions with a higher number of parameters would further improve the description of ξ_1 and ξ_2 , but it goes beyond the scope of this work. We found that the best-fitting values of the parameters b_1 and c_1 were very close to 1, thus we chose to set them exactly equal to 1. It allowed a further simplification of the analytical expression of ξ_1 with the only a_1 parameter to be optimized (cf. Table 1). From Fig. 4 it is interesting noting that ξ_1 and ξ_2 are ≈ 1 for a quite large

Fig. 5. Left and right boundaries of the non-hyperbolic region, calculated for different values of κ and r according to the generalized stability conditions, (72)-(73). (a) $r=0.3$, (b) $r=0.6$, (c) $r=0.9$.

range of κ : specifically, $\xi_1 > 0.98$ for $\kappa < 0.3$ and $\xi_2 > 0.98$ for $\kappa < 0.2$. It indicates that the unmodified asymptotic stability conditions, (55)-(56), are able to yield reasonably accurate results for these lower ranges of κ . For both ξ_1 and ξ_2 , the largest errors typically occur in correspondence of relatively high values of κ (> 0.7), in particular for very small values of r (< 0.1) (cf. Fig. 4). Both the conditions, $r < 0.1$ and $\kappa > 0.7$, are quite rare in real geophysical flows: hence, these errors are expected to be of little relevance in applications.

Fig. 5 illustrates the boundaries of the non-hyperbolic region, calculated by the generalized stability conditions, (72)-(73), for different values of κ and r . As expected, the left boundary moves upwards as κ increases, while the differences between the curves corresponding to dif-

ferent κ become smaller, as r increases. Also the right boundary heaves for increasing κ , but is almost independent from r .

As a matter of fact, it should be noted that little inaccuracies in ξ_1 and ξ_2 , may still occasionally lead to a wrong hyperbolicity check. A *false positive* exists when the approximate stability criterion wrongly detects a hyperbolicity loss. In opposition, a *false negative* occurs, if the approximate criterion wrongly detects a hyperbolic state. False negatives are more detrimental than false positives, if the stability criteria are used in a numerical treatment for the hyperbolicity loss (Castro et al., 2011; Sarno et al., 2017), as they may potentially cause numerical instabilities when the mesh is refined. A false negative occurs at the left boundary, if the best-fitting of ξ_1 overestimates its exact value, while the opposite holds for ξ_2 .

From the present numerical investigation it emerges that the maximum error on ξ_1 is $E_{\max}(\xi_1) = \max(\xi_1 - \hat{\xi}_1) \approx 0.012$, while $E_{\min}(\xi_2) = \min(\xi_2 - \hat{\xi}_2) \approx -0.004$. Considering that the residuals are everywhere small compared to the order of magnitude of ξ_1 and ξ_2 , and that they typically increase with κ , it can be found a small constant, $w > \max(|E_{\max}(\xi_1)|, |E_{\min}(\xi_2)|)$, such that the following modified regularization functions

$$\tilde{\xi}_1(\kappa, r) = \xi_1(\kappa, r) - w\kappa, \quad (80)$$

$$\tilde{\xi}_2(\kappa, r) = \xi_2(\kappa, r) + w\kappa. \quad (81)$$

yield no false negatives. On the basis of our numerical tests, a workable choice is $w = 0.015$.

4.2. Validation

Finally, we study the performance of the various stability criteria on a large numerical dataset composed of 10^6 uniformly distributed random generations of \mathbf{q} in the following intervals, chosen larger than the ones employed for calibration (Sec. 4.1): $0 \text{ m} < h_1, h_2 \leq 100 \text{ m}$, $-30 \text{ m/s} \leq u_1, u_2 \leq 30 \text{ m/s}$, $0 \leq r \leq 1$. Four stability criteria are tested:

- Criterion I: Cond. (55)-(56), derived by asymptotic analysis for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$;
- Criterion II: for the left hyperbolic region Cond. (70) derived for $\kappa \rightarrow 1$, for the right hyperbolic region Cond. (56) derived for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$;
- Criterion III: generalized Cond. (72)-(73) with best-fitting regularization functions, (78)-(79);
- Criterion IV: generalized Cond. (72)-(73) with the modified regularization functions, (80)-(81).

In Table 2 the error rates are reported together with the occurrence rates of false positives and false negatives. As it is clear from the table, the best results are obtained with Criterion III and Criterion IV, where the minimum amount of false negative cases, as expected, is achieved by Criterion IV at the cost of a slightly higher error rate (0.1682% vs. 0.1146%). It can be noted that a very small but not zero occurrence rate of false negatives is observed even with Criterion IV. This very small numerical discrepancy, which corresponds to just one false negative out of one million of random generations, is probably due to a slight underestimation of w in (80)-(81), which has been independently estimated on narrower ranges of layers thicknesses and velocities. As expected Criterion I yields more accurate results than the more conservative Criterion II. The only advantage of Criterion II is that it never yields false negatives, because it systematically underestimates the extension of both hyperbolic regions. This numerical result also confirms that the Conditions (56) and (70) exactly correspond to the external bounds of the non-hyperbolic region.

Now we consider a slightly different numerical dataset where 10^6 random generations of \mathbf{q} are selected from the same intervals ($0 \text{ m} < h_1, h_2 \leq 100 \text{ m}$, $-30 \text{ m/s} \leq u_1, u_2 \leq 30 \text{ m/s}$, $0 \leq r \leq 1$) by enforcing that $\kappa \leq 0.5$. This constraint on the layers' thicknesses appears reasonable for the majority of real geophysical flows, since it amounts to assuming that

Table 2Error rates of the various stability criteria ($0 \leq \kappa < 1$, i.e. for any flow condition).

	Overall error rate [%]	False positive rate [%]	False negative rate [%]	False negative (left region) [%]	False negative (right region) [%]
Criterion I	2.2848	1.5999	0.6849	0.6849	0
Criterion II	5.2927	5.2927	0	0	0
Criterion III	0.1146	0.0263	0.0883	0.0545	0.0338
Criterion IV	0.1682	0.1681	0.0001	0	0.0001

Table 3Error rates of the various stability criteria ($0 \leq \kappa \leq 0.5$).

	Overall error rate [%]	False positive rate [%]	False negative rate [%]	False negative (left region) [%]	False negative (right region) [%]
Criterion I	0.4333	0.2558	0.1775	0.1775	0
Criterion II	4.2665	4.2665	0	0	0
Criterion III	0.0528	0.0049	0.0479	0.0221	0.0258
Criterion IV	0.0629	0.0629	0	0	0

the thicker layer is at most 3 times larger than the other layer. The error rates of the various criteria are reported in Table 3. As shown by the table, all criteria perform even better than the case without constraints on κ . In particular, Criteria III and IV exhibit overall errors $< 0.1\%$. Moreover, as a confirmation of the trend reported in Fig. 5, it is interesting to note that the simple Criterion I, derived for $\kappa < 1$, yields reasonably consistent results with an overall error rate of approximately 0.43%.

5. Application of the proposed stability criteria to the treatment for the hyperbolicity loss

An important application of the new stability criteria is represented by the numerical treatment for the hyperbolicity loss (Castro et al. 2011), which can be implemented with any finite volume scheme by a multi-stage operator splitting technique. In the present numerical application, without loss of generality, we employ the Roe approximate Riemann solver (Roe, 1981) and a fractional-step Godunov splitting approach (e.g. LeVeque, 2004).

5.1. Numerical treatment for the loss of the hyperbolicity

The numerical solution of the two-layer PDE system can be obtained through a two-stage explicit scheme

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stage I : } \partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{0} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)*}, \\ \text{Stage II : } \frac{d\mathbf{q}}{dt} &= \mathbf{s}, \quad \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)*} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)**}. \end{aligned} \quad (82)$$

In (82) the intermediate numerical solution, $\mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)*}$ at the i -th cell and at the time-point $j+1$ is calculated by some suitable finite volume scheme, while the effects of the source term are calculated in Stage II by solving an ordinary differential equation (ODE) with initial condition $\mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)*}$. The treatment for the hyperbolicity loss, proposed by Castro et al. (2011), consists of introducing an extra momentum exchange, $F_{extra} \geq 0$ (cf. (6)), to be accounted for in a Stage III (subsequent to the two stages of scheme (82)), in which the ODE

$$\frac{d\mathbf{q}}{dt} = [0, -F_{extra} \text{sgn}(u_1 - u_2), 0, r F_{extra} \text{sgn}(u_1 - u_2)]^T, \quad (83)$$

is solved with initial condition $\mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)**}$, obtained by Stage II. If $\mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)**}$ is non-hyperbolic, F_{extra} has to be large enough to keep the solution within the left hyperbolic region. Semi-explicit expressions for F_{extra} were derived by Castro et al. (2011) by using the classical approximate criterion, (10). Specifically, it is assumed that

$$F_{extra} = \bar{c} |u_1 - u_2|, \quad (84)$$

where the factor $|u_1 - u_2|$ is treated implicitly and the parameter \bar{c} is treated explicitly (i.e. as a function of $\mathbf{Q}_i^{(j+1)**}$) and is determined in such a way that the updated solution, \mathbf{Q}_i^{j+1} , lies on the hyperbolic boundary

predicted by (10),

$$\bar{c} = \frac{1}{\tau} \max \left(0, \frac{|u_1^{**} - u_2^{**}|}{\sqrt{g(1-r)(h_1^{**} + h_2^{**})}} - 1 \right) \frac{h_1^{**} h_2^{**}}{h_2^{**} + r h_1^{**}}. \quad (85)$$

In (85) τ is the relaxation time towards the equilibrium, which can be interpreted as the characteristic time of restabilization associated to the mixing process. To reach the equilibrium within the time advancement $\Delta t = t^{j+1} - t^j$, it is required that $\tau \leq \Delta t$. Without loss of generality, it can be set $\tau = \Delta t$. For more details about the derivation of (85), we refer the reader to Castro et al. (2011).

A more accurate and, yet, more computationally expensive way to estimate F_{extra} was proposed by Sarno et al. (2017). This approach, different from the one based on criterion (10), is workable for any density ratio and is based on the iterative Illinois algorithm, where the hyperbolicity is repeatedly checked by the discriminant method and a convergence criterion on F_{extra} , depending on a small threshold, is employed.

5.2. New formula for determining F_{extra}

In this application we employ the generalized left stability criterion, (72), which describes the physically relevant hyperbolic region in geophysical flows. Since (72), with the definition of the regularization function ξ_1 (78), has an analytical form, it is possible to reach an expression for F_{extra} , more accurate than (84)-(85). Specifically, keeping (84), in order to obtain that the updated solution, \mathbf{Q}_i^{j+1} , lies on the hyperbolic boundary predicted by (72), Eq. (85) is modified as

$$\bar{c} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \max \left(0, \frac{|u_1^{**} - u_2^{**}|}{\sqrt{2g(1-\sqrt{r})\xi_1(\kappa^{**}, r)(h_1^{**} + h_2^{**})}} - 1 \right) \frac{h_1^{**} h_2^{**}}{h_2^{**} + r h_1^{**}}. \quad (86)$$

Analogous to Castro et al. (2011), the updated momentum components of \mathbf{Q}_i^{j+1} are calculated semi-implicitly by the linear system

$$\begin{aligned} (h_1 u_1)_i^{j+1} &= (h_1 u_1)_i^{(j+1)**} + \Delta t \bar{c}_i^{(j+1)**} \left[\frac{(h_2 u_2)_i^{j+1}}{h_{2,i}^{(j+1)**}} - \frac{(h_1 u_1)_i^{j+1}}{h_{1,i}^{(j+1)**}} \right], \\ (h_2 u_2)_i^{j+1} &= (h_2 u_2)_i^{(j+1)**} - \Delta t r \bar{c}_i^{(j+1)**} \left[\frac{(h_2 u_2)_i^{j+1}}{h_{2,i}^{(j+1)**}} - \frac{(h_1 u_1)_i^{j+1}}{h_{1,i}^{(j+1)**}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (87)$$

5.3. Test case of an exchange flow with non-hyperbolic initial conditions and small density ratio

An exchange flow with non-hyperbolic initial conditions and small density ratio was proposed by Sarno et al. (2017) as a paradigmatic test case to show that, for small density ratios, the numerical treatment proposed by Castro et al. (2011) not only yields less accurate results but may even change the flow structure, by modifying the signs of the

layers' velocities. Here we employ a similar test to show that the semi-implicit treatment, (87), with the modification (86), well approximates the reference solution, obtained by using the more computationally expensive iterative method by Sarno et al. (2017). The test case describes the exchange flow of two superimposed fluids with $r=0.3$. The spatial domain is $x \in [-1, 1]$ and the initial conditions are

$$h_1(x, 0) = \begin{cases} 0.1 \text{ m, if } |x| \leq 0.5\text{m} \\ 0.5 \text{ m, if } |x| > 0.5\text{m} \end{cases}, \quad h_2(x, 0) = 1.0\text{m} - h_1(x, 0), \quad (88)$$

$$u_1(x, 0) = 1.00\text{m/s}, \quad u_2(x, 0) = -3.00\text{m/s}.$$

To study the performance of the hyperbolicity treatment with the new stability criteria over a wide range of κ , the initial conditions (88) are chosen such that $\kappa = 0$ for $|x| > 0.5\text{m}$ and $\kappa = 0.8$ in the middle region ($|x| \leq 0.5\text{m}$). Non-reflective boundary conditions are imposed at $x = -1$ and $x = 1$. The numerical simulations, reported below, are performed by using a spatial discretization $\Delta x = 1/200 = 0.005 \text{ m}$, while various mesh refinements have been tested for checking grid convergence. To get stable time steps Δt , the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number was set equal to 0.95 for all simulations. Analogous to Sarno et al. (2017), to which we refer the reader for details, the advection terms of the PDE system, (1), are treated by means of a first-order finite volume scheme, based on the Roe approximate Riemann solver with the real Jordan decomposition (Roe, 1981; Castro et al., 2011). Although the scope of this numerical investigation does not include the optimization of the advection numerical scheme, it is worth remarking that the numerical treatment for the hyperbolicity loss is compatible with any finite volume

scheme. More efficient advection numerical schemes are reported e.g. by Kravavika et al. (2018). The following options for the numerical treatment of the hyperbolicity loss are tested:

- SIM-A: Iterative algorithm by Sarno et al. (2017), where the hyperbolicity is checked by the discriminant, (8), of the quartic characteristic polynomial;
- SIM-B: Iterative algorithm by Sarno et al. (2017), where the hyperbolicity is checked by the discriminant of the resolvent cubic, (9);
- SIM-C: Semi-implicit formulae, (86)-(87), and F_{extra} parameterized according to the stability criterion (10);
- SIM-D: Semi-implicit formulae (86)-(87), and F_{extra} parameterized according to the stability criterion, (72).

The Illinois iterative algorithm in SIM-A and SIM-B is run with the convergence threshold equal to $10^{-5}\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, as suggested by Sarno et al. (2017). SIM-D is run with the modified regularization function, ξ_1 , determined by (80) with $w=0.015$. The numerical simulations were carried out on a PC with Intel Core i7-9700K@3.60GHz and were run up to $t=5\text{s}$, when the steady state is reached. Table 4 lists the relevant numerical results. The maximum value of F_{extra} , reported in Table 4, occurs in the first time step for all simulations. As expected, SIM-A and SIM-B yield exactly the same numerical results, with a slightly lower run time for SIM-B. This improvement is in qualitative agreement with (Kravavika et al., 2018).

Fig. 6 shows the layers' thicknesses and velocities, predicted by SIM-B, SIM-C and SIM-D at the time points $t=0.25\text{s}$, 0.5s , 1.0s and 5.0s ,

Fig. 6. Comparisons of the layers' thicknesses and velocities, obtained from different simulations ($h_1 + h_2$ and u_1 are plotted as dash lines, while h_2 and u_2 are plotted as continuous lines). (a) $t=0.25\text{s}$, (b) $t=0.5\text{s}$, (c) $t=1.0\text{s}$, (d) $t=5.0\text{s}$.

Table 4

Maximum values of F_{extra} , steady state solutions ($t=5s$), and CPU times of different simulations.

	$\max(F_{extra}) [m^2/s^2]$	$h_1 [m]$	$u_1 [m/s]$	$h_2 [m]$	$u_2 [m/s]$	CPU time [s]
SIM-A	576.8	0.4747	0.1107	0.4981	-2.7830	210.3
SIM-B	576.8	0.4747	0.1107	0.4981	-2.7830	205.9
SIM-C	771.2	0.4769	-0.1596	0.4980	-2.7003	123.1
SIM-D	578.3	0.4748	0.1112	0.4981	-2.7830	124.6

Fig. 7. Maximum values of F_{extra} , calculated along the whole spatial domain, vs. time. Inset: values of F_{extra} corresponding to the initial time interval, $t < 0.002s$.

respectively. It is evident that SIM-C, obtained by using the approximate criterion (10), overcorrects the numerical solution. Indeed, in this simulation the initial exchange flow becomes unidirectional and, thus, arrives at a completely different steady state than SIM-B. This is due to the strong overestimation of the corrective momentum exchange, $F_{extra} = 771.2 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ (Table 4), at the beginning of the simulation, in turn caused by the low density ratio that the approximate criterion (10) cannot cope with. Conversely, SIM-D, obtained by using the generalized stability criterion (72), is in excellent agreement with the reference numerical solution (SIM-A and SIM-B), with only minor discrepancies being observed where the gradients of the solution are steep (Figs. 6(a)-(b)-(c)). The very good agreement among SIM-A, SIM-B and SIM-D is also corroborated by the comparable values of $\max(F_{extra})$: $578.3 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ for SIM-D and $576.8 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ for SIM-A and SIM-B. As well, the steady state solution by SIM-D is almost identical to the one obtained by using the computationally more expensive iterative algorithm (Table 4 and Fig. 6(d)). Fig. 7 shows the maximum values of F_{extra} , calculated over the spatial domain as a function of time. For representation convenience, the larger values of F_{extra} corresponding to the initial time interval, $t < 0.002s$, are displayed in the inset plot of Fig. 7. It can be noted that the SIM-C systematically underestimates F_{extra} for all t (except for the first time step) and, furthermore, it yields $F_{extra} = 0$ after $t \approx 0.5s$. This is due to the strong overestimation of $F_{extra} = 771.2 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ at the beginning of the simulation, which considerably modifies the flow dynamics. Differently, the values of $\max(F_{extra})$ by SIM-D are very close to the ones by the reference SIM-B. Yet, especially for $t < 0.5s$, it can be noticed that these values are slightly smaller than the ones by SIM-B. This behavior is the consequence of the fact that in the earlier time-steps SIM-D slightly overestimates F_{extra} . For $t > 0.5s$ a small time phase shift occurs between the corrections by SIM-B and SIM-D, due to minor discrepancies between the flow dynamics predicted by the two simulations (cf. Fig. 6).

Looking at the run times of Table 4, the advantage of the proposed algorithm is evident: indeed, the run time for SIM-D is considerably lower than SIM-B (124.6s versus 205.9s), with a speed-up of approximately 40% in this test case. In the light of these findings, we can state that, while the iterative algorithm by Sarno et al. (2017) remains

Fig. 8. CPU time versus relative error, $\|E\|_1$ ($t=2.5s$). (a) Iterative method (SIM-B), (b) Semi-implicit method (SIM-D).

very accurate in determining the smallest amount of F_{extra} necessary for guaranteeing the PDE system hyperbolicity, the proposed semi-implicit treatment with the generalized stability criterion represents an excellent alternative with much lower computational costs. The decrease of the computational time is even higher, when a more refined mesh is used, especially if the loss of hyperbolicity occurs in a large number of computational cells.

5.3.1. Mesh refinements and computational costs

To better illustrate it, the same test case is carried out with different mesh sizes, $\Delta x \in \{1/50, 1/100, 1/200, 1/400, 1/800, 1/1600m\}$ and refinement ratio $p=2$. The CPU times for SIM-B and SIM-D are listed in Table 5. The speed-up of SIM-D over SIM-B further increases with the mesh refinement. Indeed, while the run time of SIM-D increases by p^2 , SIM-B shows a higher increase of the computational costs as the mesh becomes finer. This is due to the additional overhead of the iterative algorithm, employed for calculating F_{extra} , as we observed that the average number of iterations, required by the Illinois iterative algorithm to converge, increases with the mesh refinement.

Table 5
CPU times of SIM-B and SIM-D, corresponding to different grid sizes.

Number of cells	Δx [m]	CPU time (SIM-B) [s]	CPU time (SIM-D) [s]	Speed-up [%]
100	1/50	9.5	8.2	13.8
200	1/100	41.8	31.4	24.9
400	1/200	205.9	124.6	39.5
500	1/400	1147.3	502.8	56.2
1600	1/800	7077.1	2043.9	71.1
3200	1/1600	48226.7	8098.9	83.2

Taking as reference the simulations, obtained by SIM-B and SIM-D with the finest grid $\Delta x = 1/1600\text{m}$, we could also estimate the relative ℓ^1 -norm errors (e.g. Leveque, 2004) of the runs with coarse grids. For a given time point j , the relative ℓ^1 -norm error of the function q is defined as

$$\|E\|_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{q}_i^j - q_i^j|}{\sum_{i=1}^N |q_i^j|}, \quad (89)$$

where \hat{q} is the coarse numerical solution, q is the reference solution, i is the spatial discretization index and N is the number of cells in the coarse grid. As expected, we observed that, for all variables $h_1, h_1 u_1, h_2, h_2 u_2$, $\|E\|_1$ decreases almost linearly with decreasing Δx . For any grid size, the magnitudes of $\|E\|_1$ by the two treatments (SIM-B and SIM-D) are comparable, although the two schemes converge to slightly different steady states, which is expected since F_{extra} are calculated in slightly different ways (cf. Fig. 7). Fig. 8 shows the simulation run times versus the relative errors $\|E\|_1$, obtained at the intermediate time-point, $t=2.5\text{s}$. As it is evident from the figure, not only SIM-D requires much less CPU

Fig. 9. Numerical solutions of the 1D Riemann problem, (90), ($t=0.2\text{s}$), obtained with the hyperbolicity treatment (SIM-D) and without it (SIM-E). (a) $h_1 + h_2$, (b) h_2 , (c) $h_1 u_1$, (d) $h_2 u_2$, (e) F_{extra} (SIM-D), (f) eigenvalues of the numerical solution (SIM-D).

Table 6
Integral means of h_1 , h_1u_1 , h_2 and h_2u_2 in the sub-domains $x \in [-1, 0]$ and $x \in]0, 1]$.

	SIM-D $x \in [-1, 0]$	SIM-E $x \in [-1, 0]$	SIM-D $x \in]0, 1]$	SIM-E $x \in]0, 1]$
h_1	0.0737	0.0737	0.1263	0.1263
h_1u_1	0.0793	0.0793	0.2585	0.246
h_2	1.4065	1.4065	0.5912	0.5912
h_2u_2	1.4855	1.4853	2.0523	2.0583

resources than SIM-B, but this advantage widens for decreasing values of $\|E\|_1$. Hence, for large-scale simulations, the semi-implicit scheme with the new generalized stability criterion is preferable over the iterative scheme.

5.4. Test case of a 1D Riemann problem with zero initial velocities

Here, we present a test case, consisting of a 1D Riemann problem with zero velocities and non-zero layers' thicknesses. This test is analogous to the wet-bed dam-break problem of the one-layer shallow-water model (Stoker, 1957) and is similar to the shock-tube test of gas dynamics (Leveque, 2004). The spatial domain is $x \in [-1, 1]$ and has non-reflective boundaries at $x = -1$ and $x = 1$. The density ratio between the two fluids is $r = 0.5$ and the initial data, hyperbolic everywhere, are piecewise constant

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(x, 0) &= 0.1 \text{ m}, \quad h_2(x, 0) = \begin{cases} 1.9 \text{ m}, & \text{if } x \leq 0 \text{ m} \\ 0.1 \text{ m}, & \text{if } x > 0 \text{ m} \end{cases} \\ u_1(x, 0) &= 0 \text{ m/s}, \quad u_2(x, 0) = 0 \text{ m/s}. \end{aligned} \quad (90)$$

The jump of h_2 between left and right states, \mathbf{q}^L and \mathbf{q}^R , in (90), is chosen high enough so that there is a non-hyperbolic intermediate region in the Riemann solution (i.e. the one directly connected to \mathbf{q}^R , cf. Fig. 9). Although the meaningfulness of a Riemann problem with non-hyperbolic regions is debatable from a rigorous mathematical viewpoint (e.g. Keyfitz et al., 2003), this test is of practical use to better study the effects of the hyperbolicity treatment on the numerical solution. The code with the semi-implicit algorithm, (86)-(87), and the stability criteria, (72), (denoted with "SIM-D", as stated in Sec. 5.3) is run with $\Delta x = 1/1600 \text{ m}$ and $\text{CFL} = 0.95$. A comparative numerical solution, denoted with "SIM-E", is obtained without the hyperbolicity treatment. To properly capture transonic rarefactions, in both codes we employed the Harten entropy fix (Harten, 1984). As expected, while the numerical code, SIM-D, is found to converge to a similarity solution, $\mathbf{q}(x, t) = \tilde{\mathbf{q}}(x/t, \mathbf{q}^L, \mathbf{q}^R)$, the one without the hyperbolicity treatment, SIM-E, yields catastrophic short-wave instabilities, noticeable from $t = 0.2 \text{ s}$ and rapidly growing with time till the solution blow-up. With reference to the time point $t = 0.2 \text{ s}$, Fig. 9 reports the calculated quantities, $h_1 + h_2$, h_2 , h_1u_1 and h_2u_2 , together with the extra momentum exchange, F_{extra} . Additionally, Fig. 9(f) illustrates the eigenvalues of the SIM-D solution (indexed in ascending order, $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_3 \leq \lambda_4$), which are useful to check the fulfilment of the entropy conditions in the sense of Lax (e.g. Leveque, 2004).

The initial states \mathbf{q}^L to \mathbf{q}^R are connected to each other through a sequence of 3 intermediate states and 4 waves. Similar to the wet-bed dam-break problem (e.g. Tseng et al., 2001; Tai et al., 2021), \mathbf{q}^L is connected to the first intermediate state by a left-going rarefaction wave of the first characteristic family (here corresponding to the smallest barotropic eigenvalue, λ_1), and the third intermediate state is connected to \mathbf{q}^R by a Lax 4-shock. As well, the second intermediate state is connected to the third one by a Lax 3-shock. Yet, interestingly, the first intermediate state appears to be connected to the second one by a composite wave, made of a 2-shock to which is attached a smooth wave of short length. Incidentally, such a composite wave is entropy admissible in the sense of Lax, while conversely a unique 2-shock wave would be not (Fig. 9(f)). Although it is beyond the scope of this paper to theoretically determine why the numerical code converges to this precise weak solution, it can

be speculated that this phenomenon probably depends on the particular choice of the Lipschitz-continuous family of paths (here assumed to be straight lines), required to extend the definition of weak solution to non-conservative PDE systems (Dal Maso et al., 1995; Parés, 2006). On the other hand, it is worth mentioning that minor effects on the convergence point might be also due to the particular numerical scheme, as signalled by Castro et al. (2010).

The hyperbolicity treatment is active at the right-going shock connecting the third intermediate state to \mathbf{q}^R , where a non-zero F_{extra} is continuously injected to guarantee the hyperbolicity of the cells immediately behind the hydraulic jump (Fig. 9(e)). As expected, the treatment causes some slight changes of the solution, especially in the second and third intermediate states. Moreover, the extra momentum, F_{extra} , enters into play in the generalized Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions across the 4-shock (e.g. Castro et al., 2010). Hence, it is expected to slightly change the shock speed, as well. Nonetheless, we observed that the speed of the 4-shock is only marginally modified in SIM-D, while a slightly larger change occurs in the speed of the 3-shock (with an increase of $\approx 3\%$ over the one of SIM-E). Finally, it is useful to compare the integral means of h_1 , h_1u_1 , h_2 and h_2u_2 , in the intervals $-1 \leq x \leq 0$ and $0 < x \leq 1$. The integral means, reported in Table 6, are practically identical in the left sub-domain, $x \in [-1, 0]$, and are very similar to each other also in the right sub-domain, with the largest difference being observed for h_1u_1 (relative ℓ^1 -norm error of $\approx 5\%$).

6. Conclusions

In this work we systematically studied the eigenstructure of the two-layer model by asymptotic analysis. A first analysis was carried out by assuming small velocity differences between the layers, from which the classical stability criterion by (Schijf and Schönfeld, 1953) is recovered for $r \rightarrow 1$. Subsequently, various asymptotic analyses were carried out by alternatively assuming that the relative thickness difference between the layers, $\kappa = |h_1 - h_2|/(h_1 + h_2)$, is either small or very large. This novel approach does not require any assumption on density ratio, r , or on the velocity difference between the layers, $|u_1 - u_2|$, and allows a new postulation of the stability criteria, corresponding to the lower and upper bounds of both left and right boundaries of the non-hyperbolic region. Generalized stability criteria were, then, proposed for intermediate values of κ , i.e. for any flow condition. The analytical structure of the generalized criteria is similar to the exact conditions, derived for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$ and $\kappa \rightarrow 1$, while the determination of four parameters was required for the characterization of two regularization functions. The best-fitting values of these parameters were obtained by an extensive numerical investigation on the space of unknowns. An excellent agreement between the semi-analytical stability criteria and the actual hyperbolicity conditions was subsequently found by numerically exploring a much larger portion of the space of unknowns $(h_1, h_1u_1, h_2, h_2u_2)^T$.

The generalized stability criteria were, then, successfully implemented in a semi-implicit numerical treatment for avoiding the hyperbolicity loss, originally proposed by Castro et al. (2011). This treatment is based on the introduction of an extra momentum exchange, F_{extra} , which has to be sufficient to keep the solution within the hyperbolic domain. Numerical investigations on a test case of a two-layer exchange flow with small density ratio showed that the new stability criterion is more favorable than the classical approximate criterion. Moreover, this new approach yields numerical results very close to the ones ob-

tained by the iterative algorithm based on the discriminant method (Sarno et al., 2017) but requires much less computational effort. A second test showed the numerical stabilization of a 1D Riemann problem with a non-hyperbolic intermediate state, which was successfully achieved thanks to the hyperbolicity treatment with the generalized stability criteria.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

L.S.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition. Y.W.: Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition. Y.-C.T.: Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis. R.M.: Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing. A.C.: Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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